

How to detect fake news on Social Media Websites?

Applying to Corona pandemic March 2020- March 2023

كيف تكتشف الأخبار الكاذبة على مواقع التواصل الاجتماعي؟

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ABSTRACT:

This study about how to detect fake news on social media and it helps social media users to identify the mechanisms and psychology of fake news to explore methods for assessing and avoiding the risk of spreading it. The searcher moderated a focus group discussion consisted of 20 young Egyptian men and women students from different faculties in 5 Egyptian universities (Cairo - Ain Shams - Helwan - Port Said - Assiut) . The researcher was also guided by the opinions of a sample of 60 academic experts and practitioners in fields of media, medicine and Technology, using several tools, including: semi-structured interview.

Results revealed that the majority of students, especially girls, pointed out that it is difficult to distinguish false news from honesty at first glance and that they trust the state radio, television and newspapers than "Social Media". Most students indicated that they sometimes shared false news simply to alert and think about with common friends, colleagues and professors, but the problem is that after many news being found to be incorrect, they remain on many sites without deleting them. Most of experts stressed that not to ratify everything published without reference to official sources reliable.

Keywords: *Fake News; Social Media; Corona Pandemic; COVID; Disinformation; Fact checking.*

الملخص:

تتناول هذه الدراسة كيفية اكتشاف الأخبار المزيفة على وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي وتساعد مستخدمي وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي في التعرف على آليات وسيكولوجية الأخبار المزيفة لاستكشاف طرق تقييمها وتجنب مخاطر انتشارها. و أدار الباحث حلقة نقاش مركزة مكونة من 20 شابا وطالبة مصريين من كليات مختلفة في 5 جامعات مصرية (القاهرة - عين شمس - حلوان - بورسعيد - أسيوط). كما استرشد الباحث بأراء عينة مكونة من 60 خبيراً أكاديمياً وممارساً في مجالات الإعلام والطب والتكنولوجيا، وذلك باستخدام عدة أدوات منها المقابلة شبه المنظمة . وكشفت النتائج أن غالبية الطلاب، وخاصة الفتيات، أشاروا إلى صعوبة تمييز الأخبار الكاذبة من الصادقة للوهلة الأولى، وأنهم يثقون في الراديو والتلفزيون والصحف الحكومية أكثر من "وسائل التواصل الاجتماعي"، وأشار معظم الطلاب إلى أنهم يشاركون أحياناً أخباراً كاذبة لمجرد التنبيه والتفكير مع الأصدقاء والزملاء والأساتذة المشتركين، لكن المشكلة أن كثير من الأخبار بعد أن يتبين أنها غير صحيحة تبقى في كثير من المواقع دون حذفها. وشدد معظم الخبراء على عدم تصديق لكل ما ينشر في وسائل الإعلام والاتصال دون الرجوع إلى المصادر الرسمية الموثوقة..

الكلمات المفتاحية: الأخبار الكاذبة؛ السوشيال ميديا؛ جانحة كورونا؛ كوفيد؛ التضليل المعلوماتي؛ فحص الحقائق.

1. INTRODUCTION:

High rates of media consumption and low trust in news institutions create an optimal environment for the rapid viral spread of information that is either intentionally or unintentionally misleading or provocative. Social Media websites are considered one of the most important new media forms but they have been active medium to publish rumors and sharing them easily Because of the phenomenon of journalistic citizen and publishing undocumented news. Furthermore social media have the ability to display a large number of news in a short time and this means that users may not take the time to search and verify each news published and often rely on these posts or likes or followers who turn the news into a popular contest and thus News that has become popular and widely shared does not mean that it is true.

The dangers of rumors are increasing that they are spreading through the age of open skies like wildfire, making confusion and a kind of media misinformation, through a process of combining facts with lies and broadcasting them, to direct people's concerns in a certain direction, in order to influence their choices and decisions and to seize their ideas to serve certain agendas. The source of rumors could be Individuals, institutions and organizations based in their work on studies and data through which to build attitudes and influence public opinion. The rumors appeared on the Internet 1988, and a new form of negative conflict emerged between people, institutions and streams. The electronic rumor became a source of informal news, especially in the absence or lack of official statements.

2- LITETURE REVIEW:

2.1.1 *Conceptual framework:*

The term Rumor is a concept that has a wide significance for its connection to many disciplines of Psychological, Sociology, Law, Anthropology, Politics, Economics, and of Psychological warfare in addition to its close connection to the revolution of communication and informatics. Hence the rumor has multiple definitions and varied angles of view about the mechanisms of its work and development and ways to prevent them ,including the definition of Dr.Mokhtar AlTohamy”Rumor is the promotion of a fabricated story that is groundless, intentionally exaggerate, intimidate, or add false or distorted information to a story that is mostly true or interpret a true story and comment on it in a manner contrary to reality and truth; The aim is to exert the Psychological influence on local, regional, global or national public opinion in order to achieve political, economic , or military objectives on a single ,multi- state or global scale.”Tohamy, 1979, P.114”.

In The Oxford Dictionary, False news is that it means non-original or false news and the multiple definitions that are considered fabricated news reports for marketing and profit or political advertising according to Wardle, Claire. 2017.“Fake news”. It’s complicated.” There is no specific definition of social media wars because of their modernity and incomplete dimensions, but can be seen as "the use of social networks to attract the attention of local, regional or international public opinion and try to influence or direct it or mislead through modern means of communication, whether Internet sites or applications of social networking during Certain time period driven by political or military factors”. Most notably, the wars of "hash tag" between Hamas and Israel during the repeated aggression on Gaza and appear during political developments such as elections, polls, laws and events, where there is no consensus where the "hash tag" begins to spread between supporters and opponents and each party tries to justify its point of view and attract the other party.

2-1.2 *Theoretical framework:*

The spread of false news was a new precedent, during the US presidential election in 2016 and many people were concerned about the impact of false information circulated on the candidates and some analysts assumed that the spread of false information played a crucial role in the final election results, according to a study of “De keersmaecker, Jonas and Roets, Arne, 2019,p.1” The US authorities have opened formal inquiries into this, as well as many research institutions to understand how this happens and its impact on the election results, including a joint study between the universities of "New York" and "Stanford", concluded that the impact of false news on the results of

the 2016 elections could be limited, and that one false news is not enough to change the conviction of the American voter candidate, and it needs to be convincing news by 36 TV advertisements.

The publishing of false news in the 2016 US presidential elections was related with a profit, In a small town in Macedonia called Phyllis, an 18-year-old high school student discovered in early 2016 that he could earn monthly more than his parents earned by creating websites to spread false news online. Wired site refers to the Macedonian boy under the pseudonym "Boras" and that he has written many fabricated articles related to the 2016 US presidential elections, and published them on Face book. Thousands of Face book users have circulated the articles and accessed article publishing sites to gain a large number of visitors. In the last weeks before the US presidential elections, the number of political websites registered by Boras in his name to spread false news, was more than a hundred sites, and were the most read and shared topics that support "Donald Trump" the Republican candidate at that time, not because Boras' endorsement or love for Trump; his reason was his search for profit, because Trump's supporters were among the most popular in sharing false news.

Also, During the US elections 2020, Twitter, Facebook, Snap and YouTube temporarily closed the accounts of former US President Donald Trump, to curb his allegations of presidential election fraud, amid riots in Washington. Francois juries, French researcher in strategic affairs said:" Media misinformation is based on an organized and planned project aimed at distorting minds and influencing the mind as well as emotions. It has only one objective: to bring suspicion, create turmoil and demoralize on all levels from the decision makers, even ordinary citizens, also makes the media a target for it to disseminate the misleading message towards public opinion". An example of media misinformation is the widely publicized claim that former Iraqi President Saddam Hussein was "at the head of the third army in the world."

Western public opinion was the victim of that "media misinformation," which paved the way for an international coalition targeting the Iraqi regime at the time. Advertisers do not intentionally post their ads through false news publishing sites, but rather advertise them through digital advertising services such as Google's Ad Sense, where they act as intermediaries between advertisers and websites, and determine how much what is paid to sites based on ad visibility and audience engagement. This has also put pressure on websites and social media platforms to take tougher measures to curb the spread of false news. Google and Face book have changed the way news is displayed so as to avoid misleading topics and technology giants have worked with verifiers to check fake news, but the main problem is that most of these efforts are trying to contain the false news after it is published, because closing its sources is almost impossible.

2.1.3 False news during Corona pandemic:

Much of our public knowledge about the pandemic of Corona comes via advanced technology, through new media that has never before been tested during a disaster of this scope and size. Because of this, we are learning more every day about the potential benefits and pitfalls of these technologies and their use during a global Just as the local social networking sites in China witnessed the launching of the warning cry of an emerging virus, but it turned in conjunction with the start of the threat of the Corona virus and its spread in the world, and before it reached Egypt, into an arena for waging a war of rumors spread across the pages of Facebook and Twitter.

Among the most prominent examples of false news promoted by websites and social media during corona pandemic at Egypt are rumors of a wrong treatment for Corona Some believed that Corona had arrived in Egypt and there was a blackout, and after its appearance, rumors continued, sometimes with more spread than announced, and at other times with possible and expected decisions such as imposing a curfew, and many others. And the "National Press Authority" warned of the terrorist group's rumors regarding the "Corona" virus, which aims to undermine the preventive measures taken by Egypt, which made it occupy an advanced place in the forefront of the countries in the world that are dealing with the Corona virus.

In fact, mental health organizations worldwide are beginning to see an increase in calls and inquiries due to the pandemic. It is clear that this crisis is already impacting our collective mental health. Information seeking in the face of danger can be an adaptive behavior. It allows us to make informed decisions about keeping ourselves safe, like looking for possible escape routes when we are faced with a threat. History has Shown that during a disaster such as this one, TV viewership typically explodes, as consumers use it not only to stay informed, but also to pass the time. This appears to be holding true for the current emergency. In recent weeks, media companies have noted increases in gaming data usage, total TV usage, and social media usage. Verizon marked a sharp 20% increase in web traffic between March 8 and 15, July, 2020.

All of this communication has led to a wealth of information about the pandemic, all available at the touch of a keyboard or click of a mouse, However, while much of this information is factual and helpful, some of it can be incorrect or even harmful. For example, on the popular social media platform We Chat, COVID-19 has repeatedly been called the “killer virus” perpetuating the sense of danger generated by the disease. And there are the posts and Tweets likening COVID-19 to common forms of influenza, minimizing the serious consequences of this virus, and encouraging people not to follow social distancing protocols.

What we see on social media is shaped by algorithms that typically highlight the content that will draw the most attention, not necessarily the content that is verified as correct. This attention to popularity over accuracy may be partially responsible for the spread of misinformation online. Not only is social media shaped by our very human reactions and interests, but it also shapes our individual mind-sets in turn. The World Health Organization (WHO) has coined a new term to highlight this phenomenon: infodemic. An infodemic is “an overabundance of information—some accurate and some not—that makes it hard for people to find trustworthy sources and reliable guidance when they need it.”¹¹ An infodemic can make people feel powerless, like there is so much information that the threat is unknowable, so it can strike anyone at any time.

This feeling of powerlessness can lead to imagining the worst outcome, or “catastrophizing,” contributing to feelings of anxiety and dread in an already anxiety provoking period. So how can we combat the infodemic, staying informed and connected while protecting our mental health at the same time? It is a tall order, but it can be done. For one thing, technology companies are stepping up to help. Their solutions range from promoting verified information to removing misinformation to attempting to avoid posting misinformation in the first place. Facebook, for example, has said they are working to block ads that try to exploit the situation, while providing the WHO with “as many free ads as” they need.

Google is also supporting the WHO by posting a special notice with WHO updates when people search for information about the virus. Twitter has added a warning label that links to the CDC when a user searches “coronavirus,” and Ticktock and YouTube issue an alert encouraging users to look to “trusted sources” for information. Even the WHO itself has assembled a coronavirus myth busting page. We can also take matters into our own hands, which contributes to a sense of control over the situation, improving our mental health. Consumer Reports recommends using the SIFT technique when faced with a new piece of information.

The first step is to stop. Take a breath before you take anything as a fact. Next, you investigate the source who is providing this information? After that, you find better coverage. Cross-check the information with trusted sources, Finally, you trace claims, quotes, and media to the original context. In other words, click back to find the original source of the information. You can find more information about SIFTing at <https://infodemic.blog/> By confirming that the information we are consuming is accurate, we can begin to overcome the feeling of powerlessness created by the infodemic, and move away from catastrophizing.

Beyond information seeking, we can also use technology means to improve our mental outlook directly. The Internet provides means to connect in a time of isolation. According to the American Psychological Association, maintaining our social networks in times of upheaval can lend a sense of normalcy while providing an opportunity to share feelings and relieve stress. If you are feeling anxious or lonely, reach out to family, friends, or even a health-care provider Use technology to access what you enjoy, to practice your hobbies, and to help maintain a sense of calm.

3- PREVIOUS STUDIES:

Study about “Impact of fake news on social networks during COVID-19 pandemic in Spain” aims to focus on the false news concerning COVID-19, spread through social media in Spain, by using the Latam Chequea database for a duration from 22/1/2020, when the first false information has been detected, up to 3/09/2021. This study has been conducted with regard to the correlation between fake news stories and the pandemic state, the motive to share them, their dissemination in other countries and the effectiveness of fact checking. The study is complemented by a qualitative method: a focus group conducted with representatives of different groups within the society.

Findings:

Fake news has been primarily disseminated through several social networks at the same time, with two peaks taking place in over a half of the said false stories. The first took place from March to April of 2020 during complete lockdown, and we were informed of prevention measures, the country’s situation and the origin of the virus, whereas the second was related to news revolving around the coming vaccines, which occurred between October and November. The audience tends to neither cross-check the information received nor report fake news to competent authorities, and fact-checking methods fail to stop their spread. Further awareness and digital literacy campaigns are thus required in addition to more involvement from governments and technological platforms.

The study about “The Role of Social Media Networks in Managing the Corona Crisis "COVID 19" and its Impact on the Egyptian Audience” from Cairo university, December 2020, aims to examine the role of social networks in managing the crisis of the Coronavirus and its impact on the Egyptian audience who follow it. The study used the survey method and questionnaire tool applying to 400 respondents. It also employed the technological determinism theory. Main results: There is a statistically significant correlation between the extent of respondents' use of social media sites during the Corona pandemic and their level of trust in these sites in dealing with the crisis.

There is a correlation between the extent of the respondents benefiting from reading Corona pandemic information on social media sites, and the degree of their satisfaction with this information, There is a statistically relationship between the motives of respondents' reliance on social media sites to know information about the Corona pandemic crisis and their opinion on the role of these sites in providing news related to the crisis. - There is a significant correlation between the respondents' perception of the role of Corona crisis information published on social media sites in changing health negatives and their motives to rely on these sites to find health information related to the crisis.

A study entitled "Unbelievable News: Public Views of False News" For Rasmus Kleis Nielsen and Lucas Grave, 2017 on "Public perceptions of false news" analyzed the data of 8 discussion groups of online news users in 4 countries: America, Britain, Spain and Finland, from each country spotted two groups: young people from 20-34 years and adults from 35 -54 years and each group consisted of 6-8 individuals during February and March 2017, they were asked about the meaning of false news and their trends over two hours. According to the study's audience, the difference between true and false news is not a decisive one, but rather a degree of difference. The study's audience described the false news as a problem caused by an alliance of news media and its politicians and platforms, considering poor Journalism, Propagandas, some ads and funded reports examples for fake news.

Many people define it as unbelievable news, including news from some sources and politicians who lie and exaggerate. There is no objective agreement on the concept of good news, highlighting the difficulty of finding solutions. -A study entitled "False News: Inaccurate and Hard to Correct. The Role of Cognitive Level in the Impact of False Information on Social Impressions" examined the effect of false information on the assessment and judgments of individuals and the relationship between the level of knowledge and the degree of change of judgments after learning that the assessment was based on false information.

This study revealed that the impact of false information cannot easily prevented by warning that the information was wrong and the nature of the impact depends on the level of individual knowledge. The study was based on a random sample that was tested on the Internet by publishing information and pictures about a nurse, claiming that she had stolen drugs and sold them, then declaring that the information was false and comparing it with a control group that was not exposed to the wrong information. Based on responding to an 8-dimensional scale of attitudes towards the nurse before and after knowledge of false information in terms of trust, respect, empathy and

intelligence assessment, it was found that individuals with a lower cognitive level adjusted their assessment and direction to a lesser degree than those with a higher level and their attitudes remained negative compared to the control group.

Other study on "Fake News or Truth? Using Satirical Cues to Detect Potentially Misleading News" pointed that Satire is a type of deception that incorporates cues revealing its own deceptiveness. This paper provides a conceptual overview of satire and humor, elaborating and illustrating the unique features of satirical news, which mimics the format and style of journalistic reporting. Satirical news stories were carefully matched and examined in contrast with their legitimate news counterparts in 12 contemporary news topics in 4 domains (civics, science, business, and "soft" news).

Building on previous work in satire detection, the study proposed an SVM based Our best predicting feature combination (Absurdity, Grammar and Punctuation) detects satirical news with a 90% precision and 84% recall . The study in algorithmically identifying satirical news pieces can aid in minimizing the potential deceptive impact of satire. "Real solutions for fake news? Measuring the effectiveness of general warnings and fact-check tags in reducing belief in false stories on social media": From Dartmouth College and the University of Michigan, This study provides several new insights about the most effective ways to counter fake news on social media.

Researchers found that when fake news headlines were flagged with a tag that says "Rated false," people were less likely to accept the headline as accurate than when headlines carried a "Disputed" tag. They also found that posting a general warning telling readers to beware of misleading content could backfire. After seeing a general warning, study participants were less likely to believe true headlines and false ones. The authors note that while their sample of 2,994 U.S. adults isn't nationally representative, the feedback they got demonstrates that online fake news can be countered "with some degree of success". The findings suggest that the specific warnings were more effective because they reduced belief solely for false headlines and did not create **spillover** effects on perceived accuracy of true news," they write.

The study "*Who shared it?: Deciding what news to trust on social media*" looks at whether news outlets or public figures have a greater influence on people's perception of a news article's trustworthiness. The findings suggest that when a public figure such as Oprah Winfrey or Dr. Oz shares a news article on social media, people's attitude toward the article is linked to how much they trust the public figure. A news outlet's reputation appears to have far less impact. In fact, researchers found mixed evidence that audiences will be more likely to trust and engage with news if it comes

from a reputable news outlet than if it comes from a fake news website. The authors write that “if people do not know a [news outlet] source, they approach its information similarly to how they would a [news outlet] source they know and trust.” The authors note that the conditions under which they conducted the study were somewhat different from those that participants would likely encounter in real life.

Researchers asked a nationally representative sample of 1,489 adults to read and answer questions about a simulated Facebook post that focused on a news article, which appeared to have been shared by one of eight public figures. In real life, these adults might have responded differently had they spotted such a post on their personal explain. “For news organizations who often rely on the strength of their brands to maintain trust in their audience, this study suggests that how people perceive their reporting on social media may have little to do with that brand,” the authors write. “A greater presence or role for individual journalists on social networks may help them boost trust in the content they create and share.”

According to a study conducted by US researchers on the phenomenon of the spread of false news via Twitter, three million people retweet the incorrect news stories more than 4 million times. The study, cited by Deutsche Welle, was based on an analysis of the content of about 126,000 tweets in English, published between 2006 and 2017. The German study ,that is published in “Science Magazine”, Indicates that counterfeit content, whether text, video, or image, has a 70% chance of spreading over real. -According to a study entitled "New applications to reduce the spread of the phenomenon of" false news", published by the Center for Future Research and Advanced Studies, Germany announced subjecting managers of pages involved in the publication of false news prosecution, and prosecute the management of the site, where the government agreed, in (April) 2017, on a bill would punish social media companies for promoting false news with fines of up to 50 million Euros.

In an attempt to contain the spread of such news; recently issued laws in several Arab and foreign countries, prohibiting the dissemination of false news through the pages of Social Media, as an example: the ban on the Egyptian Press and Media Law no.180 of 2018, on the newspaper, or the media, Or the website, publish false news, and the Supreme Council for Media Regulation has the right to take legal action against any violation on all social networking sites, especially pages whose followers exceed 5 thousand followers. Some countries, especially the UAE, have enacted legislation to combat the fabricated news phenomenon.

-A master's thesis conducted by Login Mohamed Metwally Afifi on "social media rumors and their relationship to political trends among Egyptian youth" aimed at identifying the forms of rumors on "social media" and their sources and factors of spread and ways to respond to them and the relationship between the rate of use and behavior and critical thinking skills and acceptance among young people. The study relied on Analysis of the content of a deliberate sample of rumors published on the page "This hard" to monitor the rumors on "Face book" and a questionnaire for a field sample of 400 young people between 18-30 years in Cairo and Giza.

One of the most prominent results is that "Face book" in the forefront of the sources of rumors on the Internet because most of the research sample confirmed that it is one of the most trusted communication sites. The study proved the weakness of the use of critical thinking skills to examine the information published on social networking sites and the absence of social responsibility among young people for the transmission and sharing of news before verification from its authenticity through Face book without realizing the seriousness of it. There is an inverse relationship between age, thinking skills, political awareness level and acceptance of rumors, while there is a direct relationship between the political direction and the credibility of information. Young people tend to believe what is consistent with their beliefs and attitudes. There is also a direct relationship between the rate of use of Face book and the acceptance of rumors.

It pointed out the weak role of the official media in dealing with rumors and the delay in issuing official government statements. While Magdy Dagher's study on "the role of social networks in spreading awareness of the seriousness of rumors among the public and their repercussions on the economic crises in Egypt after the revolution of June 2013" presented to the conference "Crisis Management in the Arab World: Reality and Challenges". It was conducted on sample of Egyptian users of social communication sites and revealed that the public confidence in the information published in the traditional media about the economic crises in Egypt after the revolution of June 30, 2013 greater than received through the new media, especially "Social Media".

Rather, the public's attitudes were negative towards ethical and professional standards to cover economic crises through social media. -The researcher Sally Bakr Alshalakany, at Faculty of Specific Education, Tanta University, 2017, conducted a master thesis entitled: `` rumors through social networking sites and its role in attracting young people ", and applied to 400 respondents of young Egyptian users of social media. Regarding the impact of social media rumors on the community, the results of the master thesis revealed that 64.8% of respondents believe that there is a significant and effective negative impact of social media rumors on the community, because not all

users have a critical view of what is published. It was found that 63.2% of respondents believe that the aims of the rumors published on social networking sites are disintegrating the unity of society, 54% of them believe that its aim is to destroy the value system and community peace, and 29.5% believe that its aim is to discredit and destroy confidence in the media sources.

It was also found that 57% of respondents see the rise of rumors through social networking sites in times of crisis and 27.8% of them believe that they emerge in the atmosphere of anticipation. 26% of the respondents believe that the rumors published through the communication sites have a very big role in making crises, violence and political conflict among young people. Rumors play a very big role in making division and violence among users of social networking sites, especially young people, because they are a category that can easily be persuaded by this news, recruiting and adopting certain ideas. It was found that 58.8% of respondents believe that the economic effects of rumors through social networking sites are negatively affecting the production process, 53% of them believe that they affect the export of state products. In a questionnaire published on the account of "Cyber Arabs" asked the following question: how to verify the accuracy of the information contained in particular news? .The result was as follows: 52% search Google for the truth, 31% use private sites to verify, and 17% trust what I usually read.

Fake news can take many forms, including: fake sources that use false headlines to shock or offend people on social networks to encourage likes or share; false headlines: the headline may read in more than one way or mention something as a fact, but the text of the article refers to something different. The Internet term for this kind of misleading news is "click bait," headlines or interesting images designed to attract visitors to a page or link to bring in advertising money, but can be misleading or require clicking on slides or images to access actual information, and satirical or comic news, for example: a popular satirical site called "Onions" and "News biscuit".

The NBC News agency published a report in May 2019 on the problem of false news, focused on how to detect fake news, stressing the need to assume that all news presented via social media is not true, and it included the following tips:- Question about the source of the news and is it a reliable source or not? --Search for origin and confirmation of stories spread and reviews the facts through the sites of fact-checking such as "Snoops" and "Politivact".-It is necessary to disclose false news encountered by users, but secretly, because the controversy over the validity of information publicly attracts individuals to disparate groups, to defend each side's view biased, so as not to appear naive to believe those lies.

1.3.1 The report noted step to reduce the appearance of false news, including:

-Add and delete pages and accounts you follow to know different views, even those that conflict with what you think without adoption. -Open multiple news links to overcome social media technologies that track your usage pattern and the pages you follow. -Don't assume any video you see is correct, given the development of techniques. -Check your accounts, and whether they deliberately post specific topics or misspellings, so as not to fall into the trap of accounts "BOTs". -Know your prejudices because we as human beings often believe what corresponds to our prejudices and reject the contrary.

After the spread of the phenomenon of media misinformation, which took international dimensions, as happened in the US presidential election and the media war for the "Daesh" after taking control of Iraqi cities, the world sensed its seriousness and decided to address false news through sites that investigate the truth. For example, the French newspaper "Liberation" launched the first site to check Internet news "Check News". As "Les Décodeurs" page in electronic site of French newspaper called "Le monde", the Lebanese newspaper Al-Nahar launched a campaign to combat "false news" in order to prevent misinformation and influence public opinion, for political and economic purposes. It Published articles exposing their falsity, and tips to detect them.

The supervisor of "Les Décodeurs" page" Alexander Boucher" said to the Lebanese newspaper (Al-Nahar)"Les Décodeurs" page has launched at March1 ,2017 and On February 1, 2017, the team of this page developed a special search tool at the disposal of readers Décodex as a means of "checking news and information circulating on the Internet, real or not". Decodex is the result of extensive editorial and technical work, which resulted in the scrutiny of "5,000 sites publishing false news," according to the site in its 2017 tally, which includes a 12 member team: coordinators, 8 journalists, a developer, and 2 graphic artists. A charter of 10 rules outlines their work.

When reading any news, "Boucher" raises the question "What is the source of this information? Suspicious articles often do not mention any source, and advises the reader, that" looking to see who spoke about this information. "Boucher" believes that the impact of false news can be reduced by scrutinizing any information and publishing articles exposing the hoax. He stressed that one media cannot achieve much and must be done by a maximum number of media. The editors of France24's "Observers" team also follow daily social networks to reveal the real news of the false, and this team is a result of cooperation between journalists from France 24 and enthusiasts who send recordings and pictures from different fields and countries.

In 2018, the editorial team wrote 149 articles in the field of "false news" published on the site "Observers" and sometimes it was funny news through social networks is taken seriously, and

sometimes related to the use of some kind of misinformation as a huge weapon to influence... For example since January 2018, false images of demonstrations in Iran have spread on social networks, most notably the image of a veiled woman kicking a policeman, actually taken from a film. The team advised to verify the source of the image by using the reverse image search via Google Images and video using the free Invid software.

3.1.2 Examples of sites and applications that enable you to investigate the truth

Watch frame by frame; site to watch videos and YouTube clearly with slow motion, to scan video data and details accurately. Extract Meta Data provides information about the video's publishing history and truncates and displays multifaceted images of content to help find and track matching images on another site. Among the Egyptian websites that dealt with the false news and statements the site that launched by "Al-Nahda" University in January 2019 and other site called "the true Egypt", as well as publishing periodic reports on the cabinet electronic site to respond to rumors. In September 2018, Extra News channel began its weekly "Rumors and Facts" program to monitor rumors that are marketed on social media, news sites and TV channels. It is refuted and answered professionally by analysts and specialists in the roots of the rumors and how to counter them.

Face book announced on February 6, 2019 in a press release that it is committed to curbing the spread of false news on its platform, and confirmed the removal of fake accounts, reduce the spread of pages that publish false news and stop its advertising rights. Face book has set 10 steps to verify the accuracy of news: 1-Be skeptical of headlines: false news often has attractive headlines with exclamation marks. 2-Check the link: a fake or similar link may be a warning signal for false news because many false news sites simulate real news sources by making small changes to the link. 3 - Check the source, and if the news comes from an unfamiliar source, check the section "About" to learn more. 4-Unusual news format: many false news sites contain misspellings or inappropriate layouts. 5. Look at pictures: false news often contains photos or videos that have been manipulated, sometimes, the picture may be original, but it is out of context. 6- Check Dates: false news may contain false schedules, or dates for tampered events. 7- Check the author's sources; Lack of evidence or reliance on undisclosed experts may point to a false news story. 8-If no other news source reports the same story, it may indicate that it is false. 10-News may be a joke

4. METHODOLOGICAL FRAME WORK:

4.1 Research problem and purpose:

This paper about how to detect fake news on social media websites Applying to Corona pandemic from March 2020- March 2023 and the problem with the study is the difficulty of distinguishing between true and false news in following up on an issue such as the Corona pandemic on social media, dealing with fake news that is re-shared on social media, it will help social media users to identify the mechanisms, motives and psychology of fake news and explore methods for assessing and avoiding the risk of spreading it Achieving the goal was based on an analytical field study on a sample of university students and experts

4.2 Measurement, Research Instrument and Sampling:

4.2.1 Focus group discussions

The searcher moderated a focus group discussion consisted of 20 young Egyptian men and women students from different faculties in 5 Egyptian universities (Cairo - Ain Shams - Helwan - Port Said - Assiut) from March 2020 –December2020 because Fake news has been primarily disseminated through several social networks at the same time, with two peaks taking place in many false stories. The first took place from March to April of 2020 during complete lockdown, whereas the second was related to news revolving around the coming vaccines, which occurred between October and November2020. Focus group was conducted through discussion topics related to the extent of their exposure to false news related to Corona on social media; how they distinguish between it and the facts, whether they republish it and if they rely on testing sites or official and specialized sources to verify the authenticity of the news. The searcher used qualitative analysis to get results.

4.2.2 Semi-structured interviews:

The researcher was also guided by the opinions of a sample of 60 academic experts and practitioners in fields of media, medicine and Technology during 2021-2022 years after finishing focus dissection group, in regard with how to detect and combat fake news on social media. The researcher has used several tools, including: semi-structured interview, which is flexible in directing questions and dialogue within the framework of the general lines and objectives of the organization of the interview, and telephone survey. The searcher also used qualitative analysis to get results.

5. THE RESULTS:

5.1 Results of a focus group discussion:

Results revealed that if they are skeptical about news on social media, they check it in different ways, especially the search on Google, Putting link of the page or news headline on one of the foreign or Arab news audit sites according to the content and then search for it on The students stressed the importance of thinking and realizing the mind to verify the authenticity of the news or statement, especially as universities such as Cairo University began studying a course in critical thinking. official sites or pages or by traditional media. Most students indicated that they sometimes shared false or doubtful news simply to alert research and think about with common friends, colleagues and professors, but the problem is that after being found to be incorrect, they remain on many sites without deleting them.

For example, some students have shared news on risks of wearing masks and gloves ,not all was true. The majority of students, especially girls, pointed out that it is difficult to distinguish false news from honesty at first glance and that they trust the state television and newspapers such as Al-Ahram and the seventh day more than "Social Media". Most of the students, especially in the final years of colleges, stressed that the credibility of this news pass on only fools readers, while the conscious majority consumed it by motivation of speed or as a source of entertainment or just to satisfy curiosity.

5.2 Results of semi-structured interviews:

Most of academic experts stressed that not to ratify everything published without reference to official sources reliable. Many of them advised to read about Corona virus at scientific sources and don't trust of any news on social media . In interviews with Dr. Mahmoud Alam Eldin, professor of Journalism at faculty of mass communication - Cairo University, member of the National Press Authority and Dr. Hassan Ali, president of the Association for the Protection of Viewers, Listeners and Readers, They stressed that not to ratify everything published without reference to official sources reliable.

Dr. Mahmoud Alam Eldin said that the public should have the full information that constitutes the map of the sources of media misinformation and can benefit from the experiences of countries in teaching the course of media education to develop a critical sense in dealing with the media and "social media." Dr. Huwaida Mustafa, Dean of the Faculty of Mass Communication at Cairo University, and Dr. Nagwa Kamel, professor of Journalism at Cairo University, have called to identifying the role of social media and not treating it as a source of information, media or news. It is launched to increase social networking and acquaintance and turned off the real course to guide ideas without controls or standards.

Dr. Huwaida Mustafa said that social networking sites are means of communication and not means of media. Communication is broader and more comprehensive than the media. Dr. Hassan Ali said, “Web 2 is the biggest source of rumors and Hostile channels use part of the truth and inflate it for media misinformation “.He called to Develop a media strategy to respond to hostile attacks based on precedence and free access to information from specialists and eyewitnesses, and focus on citizen awareness programs to distinguish between fake news and facts and detect Modern technology in the fabrication and ignite crises because we are in front of the media war and not neutral objective information.

According to Kazem Fayed, director of television photography at Egyptian TV that the specialist may discover the use of graphics in the image falsification, unlike the pictures taken by the camera is difficult to detect deception, which is done in several ways such as the use of a narrow lens and enlarge the image of the illusionist photographer, the number of demonstrators in the thousands but actually they are in dozens, especially that filming at night. On the contrary, a photographer can use a wide lens, imaging close-up to make the number appears few and the photo could shot from a different angle than the angle of the event.

Dr. Adel Abdul Ghaffar, former Dean of the Faculty of Mass Communication at Al-Nahda University and spokesperson of the Ministry of Higher Education, called to a positive contribution from all ministries and media in promoting the media awareness guide. He suggested media campaigns aimed at educating citizens not to get involved in promoting lies and rumors on social media and using social networking sites to serve their country and promoting them in gatherings places such as universities, youth centers, schools, information agencies and cinema.

While the media expert Ibrahim Assayed stressed on the multiplicity of false news images and how to discover such as the publication of archival photos and old videos as modern or fabricated photos in Photoshop program, or the use of inaccurate phrases or mixing opinion with the news or publishing missing news or truncated words from the context. He also pointed out to the installation of an image on different audio content and close-up shots give the false impression of the size of the few gatherings and the broadcast of fake phone calls or investigations and unilateral reports and others. He recommended with analyzing pictures and videos such as observing backgrounds and people's clothes, and whether they are consistent with the timing, weather and location, relying on professional channels and searching for information in more than one source. Ibrahim Assayed and the writer Alaa Thabet, editor of Al Ahram, pointed out that the black media represented by Al

Jazeera and others used the same image to show youth demonstrating in Qena and El warraqat the same time on Friday 27 September 2019.

Alaa Thabet confirmed the trend of Newspapers and traditional media to analysis In-depth investigation and accuracy in the dissemination of news from official sources to meet the rumors of "Social Media". The journalist Ali Gamal at Arabic BBC channel stressed that by virtue of professional experience is keen to distinguish between false and truthful news, either by reference to the original sources or the realization of the mind or the use of modern programs and technologies to discover them. Media director at Falsoo site Mahmoud Hassan told that the site's first experience in Egypt was launched by Al-Nahda University at January 2019 to correct the rumors through two teams, one to monitor false news immediately and the other to verify it through reliable sources with a focus on the Egyptian issues.

He added that there are programs and techniques to verify the authenticity of the news and distinguish fabricated photos and videos, but it is difficult to prevent lies and rumors before publishing or preventing their publication, but we can publish real news at many social sites and broadcasting them in public media. Dr. Mohamed Madkour, information systems consultant and Dr. Hossam Kamel, an IT expert, told the researcher that it is possible to track and know the source of rumors on social media sites via personal account, whether real or imaginary, through the "IP" device. They called to raising awareness with the danger of circulating rumors on "Social Media" before tracking and punishing who did the publication and dissemination.

They pointed to discussing a bill to address rumors of "Social Media" in the House of Representatives "Parliament" as well as the penalties in the laws against cybercrime. Media expert Yasser Abdul-Aziz revealed in press statements the reasons for the spread of false news, citing Social Media and identified 4 controls to face them:

- 1- A large section of the traditional media workers is not subject to the required training and qualification and therefore does not have the tools to select and disseminate the news properly, so it is necessary to give them training and qualification to deal with this type of news, with a good selection of elements working in the traditional media.
- 2- Newspapers do not put evidence or codes to explain how to deal with the statements received through social media.
- 3- Progress mechanisms of deep fraud.. It has become more means of persuasion, and therefore it is necessary to increase the degree of diversity and pluralism in the traditional media.

- 4- We have a period of polarization and targeting. Some groups and systems are tempted to use social media to deepen the unrest, requiring editorial verification of the news through two sources “source + primary source”. Journalist Mohamed Amin called during the symposium "Information in the face of rumors" at Cairo University to verify the authenticity of the news by knowing the source and search for it in more than one newspaper or official website.

He indicated that the rumor could be launched by a person, institution or private countries at the time of crisis or after the revolutions to delete the history of certain persons such as King Farouk. Dr. President of Cairo University, Mohamed El khosht , pointed to his 1996 book "Rumors: Secrets of composition and the Arts of Confrontation", in which he talked about psychological wars between countries, which is now called the fourth generation wars, which depend primarily on the rumor war and what “Fifth column” does now. He explained that rumors spread on important and difficult topics, and that the environment has a role in the dissemination and that the uneducated society is spreading rumors.

Dr. Hassan Emad, former dean of the Faculty of Mass Communication at Cairo University, called for the issuance of the information circulation law, which makes the official provide the information in a timely to the journalist or the media in a way that makes him provide full news including all aspects, which closes the door to the spread of rumors. Dr. Hassan Emad suggested the composition of electronic battalions to monitor all the submissions and published on social media of rumors and false news and the speed of response and official refutation. He referred also to interpret the decisions, laws and procedures carried out by the government at a time so as not to leave the opportunity for the enemies of the country to broadcast their highness.

He stressed that the rumors if not answered in a timely with scientific manner will spread and he pointed out that social networking sites, has become a source of news, but studies have shown that most of the information on these means either false or malicious or incomplete .He believe that the reason behind relying of the large number of public users on it is the speed of its spread and the flow of news on it to a huge and more than one source. He stressed the importance of the media to have a strong role and precedence in the dissemination of news accurately, and not to rely on social media, but on the contrary, social media must rely on the official media to get news and information. He pointed out that many rumors are launched through fake accounts and this must be codified this issue so that the creation of accounts on social networking sites must be through the identity card, to ask the owners of these accounts when launching rumors or distortion code.

6. CONCLUSIONS:

In the light of the foregoing, the researcher recommends the concerned authorities to develop an integrated strategy to quickly detect and refute social media rumors in parallel with raising the awareness of the "media" users. In health crises such as Corona, the citizen must refer to the scientific sources, especially since they are available on many sites and means such as the World Health Organization website, ministry of health bulletins, and others. The paper also advises audience with formal media and fact checking sites and programs in reading about health crises. It warns against sharing health news before verifying its authenticity due to the seriousness of its impact.

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